

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Nickel with 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime

P. K. PARIJA*, A. SARKAR, T. K. THOKDAR and S. K. MAJUMDAR

Department of Chemistry, North Bengal University, Darjeeling-734 430

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Among the organic reagents oximes are known to be somewhat specific in the formation of extractable nickel complexes¹. The present communication describes our recently developed spectrophotometric method of determination of microgram amounts of nickel through complexation with the title reagent and subsequent extraction in carbon tetrachloride, effect of diverse ions in this estimation of nickel, possibility of other solvents as extractant and quantitative determination of nickel in aqueous solutions of synthetic ternary and quaternary mixtures of ions. The reagent has been applied by others to study its reaction with iron².

Results and Discussion

Nickel(II) forms a greenish complex with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime. It is extractable into carbon tetrachloride and shows maximum absorption at 380 nm. The reagent blank does not absorb in this region. It is seen that trace quantity of pyridine or a substitute pyridine enhances absorbance; thus, 3-picoline which has been proved to offer maximum absorbance is added to the system.

The extent of extraction of nickel as its complex was investigated through absorbance measurements at different pH values in the range 0–13. Maximum

absorbance was observed when the extraction was carried out in the pH range 7–12. In this pH range a single extraction indicated a complete and quantitative recovery of nickel.

Apart from carbon tetrachloride, some other organic solvents like benzene, chloroform and ethylacetate were tested as extractants, and the corresponding molar absorptivity values were 1.172×10^4 , 0.920×10^4 and 0.683×10^4 ; compared with carbon tetrachloride, $1.202 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, they did not appear to offer any special advantage. In carbon tetrachloride the colour intensity was found to remain stable for at least 12 h (measured at 380 nm).

As regards the optimum reagent concentration, it was noted that 2 ml of 0.04% ethanolic solution of the reagent along with 0.2 ml of 3-picoline was sufficient to extract 39.5 μg of nickel in a single operation. Higher reagent concentration (upto 4 ml) had no adverse effects.

The absorbance of the organic extract showed a linear response over a concentration of 10 ppm of nickel. The molar absorptivity of the complex (on the basis of metal content) was evaluated to be $1.202 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with Sandell's sensitivity of $0.048 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ at 380 nm. The mole-ratio method indicated the formation of a 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complex. The reproducibility of the method was examined with three different samples of nickel, 19.77, 39.55 and 59.33 μg and analysing each eight times, and the mean result of each (with corresponding standard deviation) were 19.25 (0.82), 39.66 (0.82) and 59.8 μg (1.36).

Using the general procedure at pH 8, the effect of diverse ions in the binary mixtures with 23 cations and 13 anions, in the estimation of 39.5 μg of nickel were examined. Considering the deviation upto $\pm 3\%$ in the recovery of nickel as tolerance limit for the diverse ions, the results show that 3000 μg of SCN^- , F^- , PO_4^{3-} , phthalate, $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$, Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , ascorbate, tartrate, citrate; 2000 μg of Mo^{VI} , V^{V} , Sn^{II} , Bi^{III} , Cr^{III} , Mg^{II} , Sr^{II} , Ba^{II} , Ca^{II} , Cd^{II} , Rh^{III} , Pt^{IV} , Pb^{II} , Pd^{II} , Cu^{II} in presence of citrate, Fe^{III} in presence of fluoride, Au^{III} , borate, oxalate; 1000 μg of Ag^{I} and 500 μg of Th^{IV} , UO_2^{II} , Zr^{IV} , Zn^{II} , Hg^{II} are tolerated in the estimation of nickel.

Determination of nickel in synthetic mixtures : In absence of real samples microgram quantities of nickel in some synthetic mixtures were also determined. The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF NICKEL IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Sl. no.	Composition (μg)	Nickel found (μg)
1.	Ni(39.5), Cu(100), Fe(100)*	38.5, 38.0, 39.0
2.	Ni(39.5), Pd(100), Pt(100), Rh(100)	40.0, 38.5, 38.5
3.	Ni(39.5), Zr(100), Th(100), U(100)	38.0, 38.5, 40.0
4.	Ni(39.5), Zn(100), Hg(100), Cd(100)	39.0, 39.0, 40.0
5.	Ni(39.5), Mg(100), Cr(100), Mo(100)	38.5, 38.0, 38.5
6.	Ni(39.5), Ag(100), Pb(100)	38.5, 38.5, 40.0

*Plus 2 mg each of citrate and fluoride.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements were carried out with a Shimadzu PR-1 spectrophotometer and quartz cells of 10 mm optical path-length.

A stock solution of nickel(II) was prepared from $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and standardised with dimethylglyoxime. A working solution of Ni^{II} was prepared by appropriate dilution. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime was prepared following the reported method³. Buffer solution of pH 8 ($\text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4/\text{NaOH}$)⁴ was used to adjust the acidity of the aqueous phase.

3-Picoline, carbon tetrachloride and other organic solvents were distilled before use. In order to study interferences, standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their corresponding salts. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

General procedure : To an aliquot of nickel(II) (39.5 μg), were added 0.04% ethanolic solution (2.5 ml) of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldoxime and 3-picoline (0.2 ml) followed by adequate amount of buffer to make the volume of the aqueous phase 10 ml and agitated for 1 min. It was then equilibrated with carbon tetrachloride (10 ml) for 30 s. The greenish organic layer was separated and de-moistened with anhydrous sodium sulphate. The absorbance of the carbon tetrachloride extract was measured at 380 nm against a reagent blank. Amount of nickel was read from a calibration curve. To study the effects of diverse ions the desired foreign ion was added to the system before addition of the reagents.

References

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